

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.	B496		
Date:	12/1/10		
Take Off:	12:56:03Z	Z	Z
Landing:	15:19:26Z	Z	Z
Flight Time:	2h 23m 23s	h m s	h m s

Campaign: CONSTRAIN

Operating Area: North Atlantic

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Paul Field	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Core Chemistry / AVAPS training	Angela Dean	FAAM
8	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	FAAM
9	SID 2	Richard Greenaway	Uni Herts
10	CVI	Paul Barratt	Met Office
11	CVI Training	Kirsty McBeath	Met Office
12	Mission 2	Richard Cotton	Met Office
13	Aries	Clare Lee	Met Office
14	Mini-LIDAR training	Franco Marengo	Met Office
15	Mini-Lidar	Dave Pollard	Met Office
16	Manchester Cloud	James Dorsey	Manchester Uni
17			
18			
19			

	Log Sheet included
Y	Flight Folder Front Page
Y	Flight Summary
	Met Office 0600 UTC Actual Surface analysis (ASXX) chart
Y	Track Plot (GIN or GPS)
	DFLFliteStar planned track
Y	Brief
Y	Mission Scientist 1's logs
	Mission Scientist 2's logs
Y	De-brief
	ViRC chat log
	Flight Manager's Instrument Status log
Y	Flight Manager's Faults/Incidents log
Y	Pre-flight log
Y	Core Chemistry / NOx / TDLAS
	Cloud Physics In Flight
	Cloud Physics Processing
Y	AVAPS
	PSAP log
	Filters
	Printed Plots
Y	Screengrabs
	Planning charts or plots
	Images Emailed To BAe146 In Flight

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	2010-01-13	Alan Woolley	Initial version
R1			
r2			

B496 Sortie Brief CONSTRAIN

Snow diffusional growth, aggregation and sedimentation in Cirrus uncinus.

Weather Ahead of warm frontal region. The air must have high ice supersaturation so that the fallstreaks are persistent.

Sortie location North west approaches.

Timings

Pre-flight Brief 09:00

Take off: 11:00

Land: 15:30

Sortie summary

Perform a Langrangian descent, drifting with the horizontal wind to repeatedly sample Cirrus uncinus. Descend until snow evaporates. Dropsondes launched before and after the Langrangian descent to determine the thermodynamic structure. The aircraft should not be contrailing during the descent.

Sortie detail

1. Take off 11.00am
2. Transit to operating area, FL200 30-40mins
3. Sample any Mid level Cloud
4. Locating run: Identify Cirrus uncinus generating region
5. Climb above Cirrus Uncinus, or as high as possible within cloud
6. Dropsonde run: Perform straight and level run orientated with mean wind direction,
7. Cloud penetration runs: Perform a descending Langrangian descent, drifting with the horizontal wind to repeatedly sample Cirrus uncinus. The flight path is a race-track where the fallstreak is sampled during one straight. The aircraft descends during the other straight, not during the turns.(Timing look-up table required.) Drift with wind
8. Climb to top and repeat
9. Return transit.

Instrument requirements

- . • Lidar operated to identify cloud top height. No varying integration time or changing the display. Lidar reports cloud top height during dropsonde run.
- . • FWVS must be operated continuously with constant flow rate. The total condensed water content will be small.
- . • CVI operated continuously in Counter-Flow mode. No varying cut-size or changing to aerosol mode except for the Loiter run which is in aerosol mode.
- . • Nevzorov zeroed once only when at high level early in flight.
- Cloud physics to report when ice particles are no longer observed during cloud penetrating runs.

Crew List

1. Captain - Al Roberts (Directflight)
2. Co-pilot - Ian Ramsay-Rae (Directflight)
3. CCM - Dawn Quinn (Directflight)
4. Mission Scientist - Paul Field (Met Office)
5. Flight Manager - Alan Woolley (FAAM)
6. Cloud Physics - Martyn Pickering (Met Office)
7. Core Chemistry / AVAPS training - Angela Dean (FAAM)
8. AVAPS - Doug Anderson (FAAM)
9. ARIES - Clare Lee (Met Office)
10. SID - Richard Greenaway (tbc) (University of Hertfordshire)
11. Manchester Cloud - James Dorsey (University of Manchester)
12. CVI - Paul Barrett (Met Office)
13. CVI training - Kirsty McBeath (Met Office)
14. Mission Scientist 2 - Richard Cotton (Met Office)
15. Mini-LIDAR Dave Pollard (Met Office)
16. Mini-LIDAR (Training) – Franco Marengo (Met Office)

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B496** Date 24/12/10 Name PAUL FORD Page 1 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:55					TAKE OFF
13 02					7/8 Sc Below with wave body
1308					-15.5 17 left.
1316		24 Lft.			INTO CLOUDS. -34.95
131707	R1-1				START R1-1 CLOUD LAYER ABOVE 8/8 Ci 4/8 Sc below
					CLIMBS THROUGH CLOUD LAYER
132750					END R1-1
13-29					CLIMBS THROUGH CLOUD WAVE CLOUDS TO NORTH AT THIS HEIGHT -37.6 WIND @ 11 m/s 173
13:32.					JUST IN CLOUD @ 270ft -42c.
					NW 300 → SE

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B** ⁴⁹⁶..... Date ^{12/1/10}..... Name ^{RANKINS}..... Page ² of ⁴.....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1336		294ft			Drop SONAR 1
					START LAG
1338	R2.1				R2.1
					low bottom of cloud.
					CAN SEE SW.
					-47°C
					RIGHT TURN.
					LIDAR REPORTS 3000 FT
					OF CLOUD BELOW.
1342	R2.1	294ft	290		R2.1 END OF RUN
1344	R3.1	29000			R3.1
					SEE SC BELOW -49°C
1349	R3.1	294ft			R3.1
1352	P3.1	294ft			^{Hdg} P3.1 290 / 110
					CLOUD THICKENING IN THIS DIRECTION
1355					2000 FT OF CI BELOW FROM LIDAR.
					SW VISIBLE
1357	P3.1	265ft			P3.1 END

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B96..... Date Name Page 3 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1359.		26544			START R3.2 -41C CAN SEE LOWER LAYERS INSTRUMENT CPC CUI HIGH SEEMS DARK. SEE SUN - 4/8 SE BELOW
1404.		26544			END OF R3.2 @ CLOUD BASE
1407					START P3.2 LOOKS LIKE W/ AT CLOUD BASE
					HOG BACK INTO CLOUD
1412		2444			END P3.2
1414.					START R3.3 LAST RW AT CLOUD BASE SEE CLOUD BROW.
1416.		2444	111		-35°C.
					MARGE DESCENDED SLIGHTLY TOO FAST - CHANGE TO 400ft/min ΔZ = 200ft.
1419.		2444.			END R3.3 -37°C.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B496**..... Date Name Page 4 of 4.....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1420					P 3.3 Not Read OF INSURE
1422		2344			END P 3.3
1422		2344			Run 4 IN CLEAR AIR
					FWS MEASUREMENT 20°C HIGHER DP THAN PB
1430					CLEAR BELOW 6/8 Sc TO SEA 7/8 CL ABOVE
1521					LANDING
					RETURNING EARLY BECAUSE OF A/C PROBLEM

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 12-01-10

Flight No: B 496

Pre-Flighter: STEVE COWAN

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
1	✓	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
2	✓	Core Chemistry	Enter cyl content press	N ₂ = 90 bar CO ₂ /Ar = 20 bar
3	✓	Core Chemistry	Driers OK	
4		Cabin	All Racks Checked	
5	✓	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
6	✓	Core Chemistry	All Flows Checked OK	
7	✓	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
8	✓	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
9	✓	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
10	✓	HORACE	Recording data	
11	✓	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
12	✓	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
13	✓	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
14	✓	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
15	✓	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
16	✓	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
17	✓	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	
18	✓	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
19	✓	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
20	✓	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
21	✓	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
22	✗	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
23	✓	Satcom C	Checked	In cockpit
24	✓	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
25	✗	CNC	Butanol filled	
26	✗	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
27	✗	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	
28	✗	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	
29	✓	3786 CPC	DI Checked / Topped up	

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
30	✗	CCN Water	Supply filled / Drain empty	
31	✗	CCN SS cols A & B	Set to manual A0.2, B0.1	
32	✗	CCN Pressure	Normally set to 650mb	
33	✗	CCN Flow Ratios	A & B = 10 ± 0.3	
34	✓	3786 CPC	Drained	
35	✓	CPC Laptop	AIM Software set up	
36		Core Chemistry	O ₃ /NO _x /CO zeros performed Ok	
<u>External Checks</u>				
37	✓	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
38	✓	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
39	✓	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
40	✓	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
41	✓	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
42	✓	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
43	✓	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
44	✗	WAS Bottles	No. fitted and position.	
45	✓	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
46	✓	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
47	✓	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
48	✓	All other covers	Removed	
49	✓	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
50	✓	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
51		Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
52	✓	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed
53	✓	ICEX applied		
54	✓	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B496

Date: 12/1/10

Project:CONSTRAIN

Location:Prestwick

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	-----	
124549		Start-Up	0.24 kft	068	prestwick
124855		taxy	0.23 kft	065	
125050		asp open	0.24 kft	066	
125603		T/O	0.22 kft	119	
131707	132756	Run 1.1	24.0 kft	325	
132846		mpds lost	24.6 kft	326	
133638	134205	Run 2.1	29.1 - 29.0 kft	296	
133654		Sonde 1	29.0 kft	293	
134436	134941	Run 3.1	29.0 kft	112	
135151	135710	Profile 3.1	29.1 - 26.6 kft	282	
135933	140437	Run 3.2	26.5 kft	111	
140709	141231	Profile 3.2	26.6 - 24.0 kft	287	
141446	141948	Run 3.3	24.0 kft	108	
142045	142238	Profile 3.3	23.9 - 23.0 kft	147	
142242	145456	Run 4	23.0 kft	149	
151926		Land	0.30 kft	117	Prestwick

B496 Debrief
Tuesday 12th January 2010

CONSTRAIN

Snow diffusional growth, aggregation and sedimentation in cirrus uncinus.

This was the first flight of the campaign and also served as a shakedown flight for the campaign. As far as the instrumentation is concerned the flight was successful. Unfortunately several aircraft problems meant that the sortie was curtailed.

Take off at 1255 was followed by a climb up to 24 kft. The first run was started close to cloud base at 1317 (R1.1) with 8/8 Ci above and 4/8 Sc below. This run ended at 1327.

Wave clouds were observed during the climb out over the Western Isles.

We then climbed through the cloud to 29kft and dropped a sonde at 1336.

A 5 minute run was carried out at 29kft (-47C, R2.1).

The orientation for the Lagrangian descending racetrack was along a heading of 290degrees and three 5 minute straight and level legs (R3.1, R3.2, R3.3) and three 5 minute profiles (500 ft/min) (P3.1, P3.2, P3.3) were carried out drifting with the wind. The three levels of the descent were 29kft (-47C), 26.5 kft (-41C) and 24 kft (-36C). During the descent the sun was visible through the cloud and we were close to cloud base. The lidar reported up to 3000 ft of Ci below the aircraft at the western end of the pattern but nothing at the eastern end. The time range of the Lagrangian descent was 1344-1419.

We may have descended too rapidly for crystals of the size observed (less than 1 mm). It may be better to space the levels by 2000ft and perform a 5 min profile at 400 ft/min.

Because of aircraft faults we had to curtail the sortie and return to Prestwick. To complete the science flight a profile from 24kft to 23 kft was performed (P3.3) before a final run at 23kft was started at 1422.

The aircraft landed at 1521.

Paul Field.

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B496

Date: 12 Jan 10

Instruments

1. Nevz TWC no cal data for Deep-cup vane
2. No Network available at aft core rack laptops/printer
3. Cables missing from Manchester Cloud rack, no heater operating on CPI
4. Buck intermittent data – connection problem??
- 5.

Aircraft

1. No Training net
2. No Intercom service down port side
3. No power in galley
4. Possible fuel leak noticed as clear fluid seen at oat -30c running over windows at aft of aircraft on rhs.

Satcom

MPDS –

Satcom H –

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

B496 CONSTRAIN 12 Jan 2010 - In-Flight CO Calibrations

Please log fluorescence cell temperature and pressure immediately following calibration. During warm cabin flights, temperature can reach 40°C. During flight levels >FL020, cell pressure will drop (down to 5.9 at FL030)

		<i>Nominally 66 Hz/ppbv</i>	<i>Nominally 34000 Hz</i>	<i>Nominally 7.5 Torr</i>	<i>Nominally 35 - 40 °C</i>
Time	Flight level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbv)	Background Count (Hz)	Cell Pressure (Torr)	Lamp Temp (°C)
	Previous Flight			N/A	N/A
12:58:46	Pre-Flight/Gnd	64.10	35664		
13:29:32	FL221	64.905	34587.20		
15:00:51	FL230	65.594	34455.07		
Time	Flight level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbv)	Background Count (Hz)	Cell Pressure (Torr)	Lamp Temp (°C)

Pre-Flight & In-Flight comments/faults report

CO Zero - 12:30:05 - 12:40:10	
CO Monitor averaged zero (either in Hz or ppbv)	: <u> 0.4 </u>
NOx monitor averaged zero (ppbv)	: <u> 1.15 </u>
Ozone Monitor averaged zero (ppbv)	: <u> -0.3 </u>
CO Calibrations on automatic repeat?	: NO
End pressures: CO2/AR 160 bar N2 88 bar	

B496 11:31:27-15:20:39

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

ARIES flight log

Flight: B496

page 1 of

Date: 12/01/10

Operator(s): CLARE LEE

Res: km²

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: CONSTRAIN (NW Scotland)

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
12:59:48	transit			closed	71.0	30.9	CAVIAR NZ 30s
13:00:59				open			30s CH, 30s N, 30s Z bit of joggling due to pilot / MIS chat.
13:16:39	transit slow profile			open	60.9	30.6	CAVIAR NZ 30s.
13:17:07	R1			open			script continued into run. FL240
13:31:12	P ↑			open	60.9	24.6	CAVIAR NZ 30s. in ascent.
13:	R 2.1			open	60.9		FL280 continue script.
13:42:14	slow turn to right						continue script. Seemed to hang
13: 49:17				closed	41.6	5.8	CAVIAR NZ 30s
13:52:14	descent P ↓						
13:57:20				open	41.9	-1.0	HOB stabilised + opened shutter
14:04:14							Still in lower layer of Ci ~ 2 → 3 kft below, lots above. + Scattered Cu ~ 3 kft above Scay, otherwise clear. Ci above at all times.
14:12:41	End P.						Stopped science - going back due to leaking plane.
14:29							
14:32:59					41.6	-8.4	CAVIAR NZ 30s. - investigating diff settings.
14:35:24							CAVIAR Prof: Zen 20s CH, 20s Z
14:41:55				open closed.			Stopped taking data.

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

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Range: 320
Tilt: +0.00
Gain: Min
Stand-by

80 160 240 320

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Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 320
Tilt: +0.00
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- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]

Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25

Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 320
Tilt: +0.00
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
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Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

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Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radars Search Define Back Fwd Step Back Fwd 25 Data Accept Filter 1

Range: 320
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

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- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

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Data Accept: Filter 1

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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

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- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

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Data Accept: Filter 1

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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

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Range: 320
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

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Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: Filter 1

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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

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Range: 320
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- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

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Data Accept: Filter 1

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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

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Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

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- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

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Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25

Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 320
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

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Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]

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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

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Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
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- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
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Radars Search Define Back Fwd Step Back Fwd 25 Data Accept Filter 1

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- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

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- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

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- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
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- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

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Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25

Data Accept: Filter 1

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- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

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Search: Define Back Fwd Step: Back Fwd 25 Data Accept: Filter 1

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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

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- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define Back Fwd Step: Back Fwd 25 Data Accept: Filter 1

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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

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- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]

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Data Accept: Filter 1

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Range: 320
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

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- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
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Data Accept: Filter 1

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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

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- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

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- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

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Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]

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Data Accept: Filter 1

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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define Back Fwd Step: Back Fwd 25 Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 320
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: Filter 1

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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

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Range: 320
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define Back Fwd
Step: Back Fwd 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define Back Fwd Step: Back Fwd 25 Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 320
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- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]

Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25

Data Accept: Filter 1

Range: 320
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(0 Msgs)

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Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

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Gain: Min
Stand-by

80 160 240 320

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(2012 Msgs)

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(7314 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(12480 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(17555 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radars Search Define Back Fwd Step Back Fwd 25 Data Accept Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(22716 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(27781 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(32870 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Bar]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(38032 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Bar]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(43110 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define Back Fwd Step: Back Fwd 25 Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(48279 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(53343 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Bar]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(58430 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Legend]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(63588 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
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1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(68665 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define Back Fwd Step: Back Fwd 25 Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(73755 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(78839 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define Back Fwd Step: Back Fwd 25 Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(83998 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(89082 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Bar]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(94478 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(99972 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(105478 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(110878 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radars Step: 25 Data Accept: Filter: 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(116378 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(121798 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(127278 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(132784 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Bar]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(138192 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(143683 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Bar]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(149187 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(154584 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define Back Fwd Step: Back Fwd 25 Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(160080 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(165582 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(170976 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(176483 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(181975 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(187370 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define Back Fwd Step: Back Fwd 25 Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(192871 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(198373 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(203772 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(209274 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(214692 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(220174 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(225671 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(231086 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(236575 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(242077 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(247479 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0) [-] [] [X]

Radar Filter

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

A semi-circular radar display with a black background and white grid lines. The grid consists of concentric semi-circles and radial lines. At the bottom of the display, there are numerical labels 1, 3, 4, and 5. A small green target is visible in the lower-left quadrant of the radar.

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(252979 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(258477 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(263879 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radar Search Define Back Fwd Step Back Fwd 25 Data Accept Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(269374 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(274873 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(280270 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(285769 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(291193 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Radars Search Define [Back] [Fwd] Step [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(296672 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(302177 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(307585 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(313070 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(318571 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(323978 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(329476 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0) [-] [] [X]

Radar Search Define [Back] [Fwd] Step [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(334983 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Radars [Icons] Search [Define] [Back] [Fwd] Step [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept [Filter] 1

WEATHER [Color Legend]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(340387 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(345892 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(351299 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(356794 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: Filter 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Bar]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(362300 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(367698 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(373198 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0) [-] [] [X]

Filter

WEATHER

Range: 5
 STABILIZATION FAULT
 Gain: Max
 WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(378700 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radars:

Search: Define

Step: 25

Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(384094 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radar Search Define [Back] [Fwd] Step [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

A semi-circular radar display with a grid. The grid has concentric circles representing range (labeled 1, 3, 4, 5) and radial lines representing bearing. Several green returns are visible, indicating weather. One prominent return is at approximately 30 degrees bearing and 2.5 range units. Another is at approximately 60 degrees bearing and 4.5 range units. A third, smaller return is at approximately 10 degrees bearing and 1.5 range units. The text 'WX' is displayed in the lower-left area of the radar display.

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(389596 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(395015 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(400491 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Bar]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(405985 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(411479 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radars: Radar Passes

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]

Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25

Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(416873 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(422372 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(427873 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Radar Search Define [Back] [Fwd] Step [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 - Recording(433266 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(438770 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(444270 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radars: Radar,

Search: Define, Back, Fwd

Step: Back, Fwd, 25

Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(449667 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(455169 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Legend]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

A semi-circular radar display with a black background and a white grid. The grid consists of concentric circles and radial lines. Several bright green returns are visible, primarily in the upper-left and upper-right quadrants. The radial axis is labeled with the numbers 1, 3, 4, and 5 at the bottom.

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(460586 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Bar]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

A semi-circular radar display with a black background and a white grid. The grid consists of concentric circles and radial lines. The radial lines are labeled with the numbers 1, 3, 4, and 5 at the bottom. Several bright green returns are visible, primarily in the upper right and upper left quadrants. A yellow box labeled 'WEATHER' is positioned above the radar. To the left of the radar, there is yellow text: 'Range: 5', 'STABILIZATION FAULT', 'Gain: Max', and 'WX'. The radar is part of a window titled 'Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)' which has a toolbar with buttons for 'Search', 'Step', and 'Data Accept', along with various navigation icons.

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(466078 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: Filter 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Legend]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(471578 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: Filter 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Bar]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(476979 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(482482 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(487982 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Radars [Icons] Search [Define] [Back] [Fwd] Step [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept [Filter] 1

WEATHER [Color Legend]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(493388 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(498887 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Radar 25 Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(504300 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(509791 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radars Search Define Back Fwd Step Back Fwd 25 Data Accept Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(515289 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Radar Search Define [Back] [Fwd] Step [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(520693 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(526193 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Radar Search Define [Back] [Fwd] Step [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(531696 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: Filter 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Legend]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(537102 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(542603 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define Back Fwd Step: Back Fwd 25 Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(548015 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(553501 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radar Search Define Back Fwd Step Back Fwd 25 Data Accept Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(558999 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(564408 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radars:

Search: Define

Step: 25

Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(569905 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(575401 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radars Search Define Back Fwd Step Back Fwd 25 Data Accept Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(580805 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Radar

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]

Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25

Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(586306 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Legend]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(591807 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(597211 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Radar Search Define [Back] [Fwd] Step [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(602710 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radars Page Search Define Back Fwd Step Back Fwd 25 Data Accept Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(608122 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Radar Search Define [Back] [Fwd] Step [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(613612 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Radar Search Define [Back] [Fwd] Step [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(619118 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(624514 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Legend]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(630019 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Radar Search Define [Back] [Fwd] Step [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(635520 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Legend]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(640913 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(646412 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(651834 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(657314 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(662817 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radars:

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]

Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25

Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(665863 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(670121 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(675625 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define Back Fwd Step: Back Fwd 25 Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(681121 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(686522 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Legend]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(692017 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(697437 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Legend]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(702927 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Legend]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(708432 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(713830 Msgs)

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(719338 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0) [-] [] [X]

Radar Search Define [Back] [Fwd] Step [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(724759 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0) [-] [] [X]

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: Filter 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Legend]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(730247 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(735752 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(741152 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Radar Search Define [Back] [Fwd] Step [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(746652 Msgs)

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(752149 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(757546 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radars Search Define Back Fwd Step Back Fwd 25 Data Accept Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(763045 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Legend]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(768546 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Radars [Icons] Search [Define] [Back] [Fwd] Step [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept [Filter] 1

WEATHER [Color Legend]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(773943 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0) [-] [] [X]

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Legend]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(779442 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(784943 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Radars Search Define [Back] [Fwd] Step [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(790341 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(795840 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(801337 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Radars:

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]

Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25

Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(806743 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radars Page Search Define Back Fwd Step Back Fwd 25 Data Accept Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(812244 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0) [-] [] [X]

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: Filter 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Legend]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(817651 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Buttons: Radar, Pages, Search (Define, Back, Fwd), Step (Back, Fwd, 25), Data Accept (Filter, 1)

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(823147 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(828657 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons] WEATHER [Color Legend]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(834058 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(839556 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(844972 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(850458 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(855967 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(861366 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(866863 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Radars: [Radar] [Passo]

Search: [Define] [Back] [Fwd]

Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25

Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(872372 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(877772 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Bar]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

A semi-circular radar display with a black background and a white grid. The grid consists of concentric circles and radial lines. The radial lines are labeled at the bottom with the numbers 1, 3, 4, and 5. Several bright green returns are visible, primarily in the upper half of the display, indicating weather or other radar returns.

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(883271 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(888688 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Radar Search Define [Back] [Fwd] Step [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(894175 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Legend]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(899671 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radars Page

Search: Define Back Fwd

Step: Back Fwd 25

Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(905081 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Radars

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]

Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25

Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(910566 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(916066 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(921473 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 - Recording(926965 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

- LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
 - Dataset1 - Recording(932474 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(937877 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Radars Search Define [Back] [Fwd] Step [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(943385 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(948794 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radars Pulse Search Define Back Fwd Step Back Fwd 25 Data Accept Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(954291 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Legend]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(959792 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Legend]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(965195 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(970696 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(976195 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

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Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Legend]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(981595 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Radars [Icons] Search [Define] [Back] [Fwd] Step [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept [Filter] 1

WEATHER [Color Legend]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(987096 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(992590 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(997985 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radars Search Step Data Accept

Define Back Fwd Back Fwd 25 Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1003488 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radars:

Search: Define

Step: 25

Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1008983 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]

Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25

Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

A semi-circular radar display with a black background and white grid lines. The grid consists of concentric arcs and radial lines. There are several bright green returns, most notably a large cluster on the left side and a few smaller ones on the right. A red return is visible near the bottom center. The radial axis is labeled with the numbers 1, 3, 4, and 5 at the bottom.

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1014379 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1019876 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1025376 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1030775 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1036284 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1041687 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1047196 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1052616 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1058105 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1063608 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1069008 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1074502 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radars: Radar, Passes

Search: Define, Back, Fwd

Step: Back, Fwd, 25

Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1080009 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Radars: [Radar] [Passo]

Search: [Define] [Back] [Fwd]

Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25

Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1085401 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1090905 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1096405 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1101802 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Radar Search Define [Back] [Fwd] Step [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1107306 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1112723 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1118207 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1123703 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1129116 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1134608 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1140114 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radars: Radar,

Search: Define, Back, Fwd

Step: Back, Fwd, 25

Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1145509 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1151020 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1156517 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radars Search Define Back Fwd Step Back Fwd 25 Data Accept Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1161922 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1167433 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1172842 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1178346 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1183760 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1189248 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1194754 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1200153 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1205662 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1211167 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1216565 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radars:

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]

Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25

Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1222075 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1227475 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1232982 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1238485 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1243885 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1249391 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1254798 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1260297 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1265805 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1271209 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1276717 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1282120 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1287631 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1293133 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1298542 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1304044 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1309446 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1314958 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1320369 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1325861 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1331361 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1336762 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1342262 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1347759 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1353155 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1358656 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1364153 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1369549 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1375055 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

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Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]

Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25

Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1380561 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1385968 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1391477 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1396885 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1402395 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Legend]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

A semi-circular radar display with a black background and white grid lines. A green target is visible in the upper-left quadrant. The horizontal axis at the bottom is labeled with the numbers 1, 3, 4, and 5.

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

[-] [] [X]

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

Radar [Icons]

WEATHER [Color Legend]

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1405955 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1408008 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
W/S Only

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1412978 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
W/S Only

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1417861 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radars Page

Search: Define Back Fwd

Step: Back Fwd 25

Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
W/S Only

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1422813 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
W/S Only

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1427787 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
W/S Only

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1432666 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
W/S Only

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1432987 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
W/S Only

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1432987 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd] Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25 Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
W/S Only

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1432987 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Radars Search Define Back Fwd Step Back Fwd 25 Data Accept Filter 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
W/S Only

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1432987 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

Search: Define [Back] [Fwd]
Step: [Back] [Fwd] 25
Data Accept: [Filter] 1

WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
W/S Only

1 3 4 5

LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
Dataset1 - Recording(1432987 Msgs)

Dataset1 (LP708-1 Card #0)

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WEATHER

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
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LP7081Card1 (LP708-1 Card #0)
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